

Effect of Prandtl Number and Inclination Angle on MHD Natural Convection in Inclined Open Square Cavity

Sheikh Anwar Hossain^{1*}, M. A. Alim² and Satrajit Kumar Saha³

¹*Ishwardi Government College, Pabna, Bangladesh.*

²*Department of Mathematics, BUET, Dhaka, Bangladesh.*

³*Department of Mathematics, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh.*

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Author SAH designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Authors MAA and SKS managed the analyses of the study. Author SKS managed the literature searches. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Article Information

DOI: 10.9734/PSIJ/2017/33067

Editor(s):

- (1) Daniel Beysens, OPUR International Organization for Dew Utilization, France.
- (2) Stefano Moretti, School of Physics & Astronomy, University of Southampton, UK.

Reviewers:

- (1) John Abraham, University of St. Thomas, United States.
- (2) N. Nithyadevi, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, India.
- (3) Promise Mebine, Niger Delta University, Nigeria.

Complete Peer review History: <http://www.sciencedomain.org/review-history/19393>

Original Research Article

Received 29th March 2017
Accepted 22nd May 2017
Published 7th June 2017

ABSTRACT

MHD natural convection and fluid flow in a two-dimensional open and inclined square cavity with a heated circular cylinder was considered in this work. The opposite wall to the opening side of the cavity was first kept to constant heat flux q , at the same time the surrounding fluid interacting with the aperture was maintained to an ambient temperature T_{∞} . The top and bottom wall was kept to low and high temperature respectively. As a result a natural convection is formed in the cavity due to buoyancy force and temperature difference in the cavity. The governing equations for mass, momentum and energy conservation are expressed in a normalized primitive variables formulation. The streamlines and isotherms are produced, heat transfer parameter Nu are obtained for Prandtl number $Pr = 0.72, 2, 5, 7$ and inclination angles from $0^{\circ}, 5^{\circ}, 20^{\circ}, 35^{\circ}, 50^{\circ}$ for fixed Hartmann number 60. The results are presented in graphical as well as tabular form. In the result it is found that heat flux is increasing function of Prandtl number Pr , while Rayleigh number is 10000 and heat flux is maximum when inclination angle is 5° . It is observed that fluid moves counterclockwise

*Corresponding author: E-mail: sheikhanwarhossain@gmail.com;

around the cylinder. Various recirculations are formed around the cylinder and one small vortex is formed into the flow field for 50° inclination and $Pr = 0.72$ near the cylinder. The almost all isotherm lines are concentrated at the right lower corner of the cavity. The present result agree with the existent heat transfer and boundary layer theory.

Keywords: MHD; finite element method; natural convection; open cavity.

1. INTRODUCTION

MHD natural convection in open cavity becomes very important in many scientific and engineering problems, because it's wide range of applications in Physical science and thermal engineering problems. For example, in the design of electronic devices, solar thermal receivers, uncovered flat plate solar collectors having rows of vertical strips, geothermal reservoirs, etc. Several experimental and numerical investigation have been presented for describing the phenomenon of natural convection in open cavity for two decades. Prandtl number is named after Ludwig Prandtl, who introduced the concept of boundary layer in 1904 and made significant contributions to boundary layer theory.

Finite element analysis based on Galerkin weighted Residual method is used to solve the problem. Boussinesq approximation is used to optimize the error. Using the consistent set of boundary conditions and values of parameters it is observed that the heat transfer rate is a increasing function of Prandtl number Pr in the cavity. The results are presented in graphical as well as tabular form.

Alfven Hannes [1] is the pioneer of the field of MHD for which he received the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1970. A numerical solution of the Navier –Stokes equations using finite element technique has been done by C. Taylor and P. Hood [2] in 1973. Chan and Tien [3] investigated shallow open cavities and made a comparison study using a square cavity in an enlarged computational domain. In the result they observed that for a square open cavity having an isothermal vertical side facing the opening and two adjoining adiabatic horizontal sides. Satisfactory heat transfer results could be obtained, especially at high Rayleigh numbers. Ostrach [4]. Finite Element Analysis is well discussed by Buchanan, G. R., [5] in the text Finite Element Analysis, McGraw Hill, Schaum's out lines, ISBN 0-07-008714-8, 1994. Mohammad, A. [6] investigated inclined open square cavities, by considering a restricted computational domain. The gradients of both

velocity components were set to zero at the opening plane in that case which were different from that of Chan and Tien. In the result he found that heat transfer was not sensitive to inclination angle and the flow was unstable at high Rayleigh numbers and small inclination angles. Boussinesq approximation is used to optimize the error in numerical solution of a like problem by E. M. Sparrow and J. P. Abraham [7]. Roy and Basak [8] have done an analysis on natural convection flows in a square cavity with non-uniformly heated walls. Sarris et al. [9] studied MHD natural convection in a laterally and volumetrically heated square cavity. Bilgen and Oztop [10] studied numerically the steady-state heat transfer by natural convection in partially open inclined square cavities.

Ben Nakhi A, et al. [11], studied a computational study of steady laminar natural convective fluid flow in a partially open square enclosure with a highly conductive thin fin of arbitrary length attached to the hot wall at various levels. They considered the horizontal walls and the partially open vertical adiabatic wall while the vertical wall facing the partial opening is isothermally hot. The investigation was on the flow modification due to the (i) attachment of a highly conductive thin fin of length equal to 20%, 35% or 50% of the enclosure width, attached to the hot wall at different heights and (ii) variation of the size and height of the aperture located on the vertical wall facing the hot wall. They also examine the impact of Rayleigh number ($10^4 \leq Ra \leq 10^7$) and inclination of the enclosure. To solve the problem numerically they used finite volume method of numerical techniques. They observed that the presence of the fin has counteracting effects on flow and temperature fields. These effects are dependent in a complex way, on the fin level and length, aperture altitude and size, cavity inclination angle and Rayleigh number. Furthermore, a longer fin causes higher rate of heat transfer to the fluid, although the equivalent finless cavity may have higher heat transfer rate. In general, the volumetric flow rate and the rate of heat loss from the hot surfaces are interrelated and are increasing functions of Rayleigh number.

S. Pervin and R. Nasrin [12], studied MHD free convection and heat transfer for different values of Raleigh numbers Ra and Hartmann numbers Ha in a rectangular enclosure. Their results show that the flow pattern and temperature field are significantly dependent on the used parameters. Hossain, S. A. and Alim M. A. [13], studied on natural convection heat transfer in an open rectangular cavity containing a heated circular cylinder. In the result they found that the heat transfer increases as Grashof number increases from 10^3 to 10^6 . Saha S. C. [14] studied thermo-magnetic convection and heat transfer of paramagnetic fluid in an open square cavity with different boundary conditions. His results show the Effects of Magnetic Rayleigh number, Prandtl number on the flow pattern and isotherm as well as on the heat absorption graphically. He found that the heat transfer rate is suppressed in decreased of the Magnetic Rayleigh number.

1.1 Objectives

The objectives of this study are to analyze numerically the effect of Prandtl number Pr and inclination angle of the cavity on MHD natural

convection heat transfer and fluid flow inside the cavity by visualizing the fluid flow in terms of isotherms and streamlines respectively. To develop a Mathematical model regarding this problem on MHD natural convection.

1.2 Physical Figure of the Problem

In this study heat transfer and the fluid flow in a two-dimensional open rectangular cavity of length L was considered, which is shown in the following schematic diagram in Fig. 1.

1.3 Mathematical Formulation

The flow inside the cavity is assumed to be two-dimensional, steady, laminar, and incompressible and the fluid properties are to be constant. The radiation effects are taken negligible and the Boussinesq approximation is used. The dimensionless governing equations describing the flow are as follows:

$$\text{Continuity equation: } \frac{\partial U}{\partial X} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial Y} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the physical problem

Momentum equations:

$$U \frac{\partial U}{\partial X} + V \frac{\partial U}{\partial Y} = - \frac{\partial P}{\partial X} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{Gr}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial X^2} + \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial Y^2} \right) + \theta \sin \phi \quad (2)$$

$$U \frac{\partial V}{\partial X} + V \frac{\partial V}{\partial Y} = - \frac{\partial P}{\partial Y} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{Gr}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial X^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial Y^2} \right) + \theta \cos \phi + Ra Pr \theta - Ha^2 Pr v \quad (3)$$

Energy equation:

$$U \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial X} + V \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial Y} = \frac{1}{Pr \sqrt{Gr}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial X^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial Y^2} \right) \quad (4)$$

At Bottom wall: $U = V = 0$; $\theta = 1$, $0 \leq X \leq 1$ and $Y = 0$

At Top wall: $U = V = 0$; $\theta = 0$, $0 \leq X \leq 1$ and $Y = 1$

At the left wall: $U = V = 0$; heat flux $q = 150$, $X = 0$, $0 \leq Y \leq 1$

At the right side & open side: Convective Boundary Condition (CBC), $P = 0$.

1.3.1 Used non-dimensional scales

$$X = \frac{x}{L}, \quad Y = \frac{y}{L}, \quad U = \frac{u}{U_0}, \quad V = \frac{v}{U_0},$$

$$P = \frac{P - P_\infty}{\rho U_0^2}, \quad \theta = \frac{T - T_\infty}{\Delta t}, \quad Pr = \frac{\nu}{\alpha}, \quad Gr = \frac{g \beta \Delta T L^3}{\nu^2}$$

$$Ha = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma L^3 B^2}{\mu}}, \quad dr = \frac{D}{L}, \quad \Delta t = (T_s - T_\infty),$$

$$\Delta t = \frac{qL}{K}$$

1.3.2 Used heat transfer characteristics

The flow field in MHD natural convection is governed by the dimensionless Rayleigh Number Ra. The Rayleigh number is defined as the product of Grashof number and Prandtl number.

$$\text{i.e. Ra} = Gr.Pr$$

Here the Grashof number represents the ratio of the buoyancy force to the viscous force acting on the fluid and the reference velocity U_0 is related to the buoyancy force term and is defined as

$$U_0 = \sqrt{g \beta L (T_w - T_\infty)}$$

Here, g is the gravitational acceleration, β is volumetric thermal expansion coefficient, $1/T$ ($\beta = 1/T$ for ideal gas), T_s is temperature at the surface, T_∞ is the temperature of the fluid sufficiently far from the wall. The Nusselt number Nu is also an important non-dimensional parameter to be computed for heat transfer analysis in natural convection flow. The Nusselt number for natural convection is a function of the Grashof number only. The local Nusselt number

Nu can be obtained from the temperature field by applying the following function $Nu = -\frac{1}{\theta(0, Y)}$

The overall or average Nusselt number was calculated by integrating the temperature gradient over the heated wall as follows:

$$Nu_{av} = -\int_0^1 \frac{1}{\theta(0, Y)} dy$$

Pr is a heat transfer characteristics in the flow field of natural convection. Since the dimensionless Prandtl Number Pr is the ratio of kinematic viscosity to thermal diffusivity.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Finite Element Methods (FEM) is a method to solve differential equations numerically which can be applied to many problems in engineering and scientific fields. Galerkin's weighted residual finite element method is applied to discretize the non-dimensional governing equations. Boussinesq approximation is used to optimize the error in the numerical solution. Triangular mesh is used to obtain the solution due to this mesh can use in any complicated domain of solution but rectangular mesh can be used in rectangular domain only.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A numerical study has been done on steady state MHD natural convection flow in a two-dimensional square open cavity with inclination angle. The left vertical wall of the cavity is at a constant heat flux as shown in Fig. 1. A heated circular cylinder is placed at the centre of the cavity. The bottom and top walls are kept at high and cool temperature respectively. Two-dimensional Navier–Stokes equations along

with the energy equations are the governing equations and are solved using Gelarkin's finite element method. The results are also presented in terms of streamlines and isotherm patterns. The effects of variations of Prandtl number and inclination angles of the cavity are predicted. The results are computed for $Ha = 60$, $Ra = 10^4$, at $Pr = 0.72, 2.0, 5.0$ and 7.0 while inclination angles of the cavity are $\phi = 0^\circ, 5^\circ, 20^\circ, 35^\circ, 50^\circ$ with hot temperatures at the bottom wall and cylinder. Other physical properties are assumed to be constant. Here the parametric analysis for a wide range of governing parameters shows consistence performance of the present numerical approach to compute as temperature profiles and streamlines. All the results of this work are computed for $dr = 0.2$.

3.1 Effects of Prandtl Number Pr and Inclination Angles

Due to increase of inclination angle, complex flow pattern characteristics were found for various Prandtl numbers Pr. This profile of isotherms, streamlines and inclination angles $0^\circ, 5^\circ, 20^\circ, 35^\circ$ and 50° of the cavity are presented in Figs. from 3 to 7. In the most cases the isotherms are remained at the right half of the cavity and the almost all isotherms are concentrated at right lower corner of the cavity. Recirculations are formed around the cylinder in the cavity counterclockwise. But one small vortex is formed in the cavity for $Pr = 0.72$ and angle

50° . The Fig. 2 shows that the fluid flow counterclockwise around the cylinder.

Here the total heat flux decreases mainly for higher inclination angles. This is because of the opening side become the upper side and the temperature difference become less than those of previous position and buoyancy effect is less than before. It is also observed that heat flux increases for higher Prandtl numbers. The isotherms and streamlines for $dr = 0.2$, $Pr = 0.72$, $Ha = 30$, $T_h = 330^\circ\text{K}$, $T_c = 276^\circ\text{K}$ while inclination angles $\phi = 0^\circ, 5^\circ, 20^\circ, 35^\circ, 50^\circ$ are shown in Figs. from 3 to 7. In all cases heat flux is decreases for higher inclination angles. The most of isotherms are concentrated at the right lower corner of the cavity. The fluid flows form recirculations around the cylinder in the cavity, but one small vortex is formed at right side of the cylinder for the inclination angle 50° and $Pr = 0.72$ and 2.0 . The streamline are in laminar form and there is no turbulence in the flow field in this study.

The total heat flux at the open cavity for Rayleigh numbers $= 10^4$, inclination angles range of 0° to 50° and $Pr = 0.72, 2.0, 5.0, 7.0$ are shown in the line graphs from Figs. 8 to 12 respectively and these results are tabulated in the Table 1. The results show that heat flux decrease as inclination angles increase from 5° to 50° . The heat flux is maximum for the maximum Prandtl number $Pr = 7$ and inclination angle 5° .

Fig. 2. Streamlines with direction around the cylinder for $Pr = 1$, $Ha = 60$, $q = 150$, $\phi = 15^\circ$

Fig. 3. (a) Isotherms & (b) Streamlines in the cavity for various Pr and $Ha = 60$, $Ra=10^5$, $\phi = 0^\circ$

Fig. 4. (a) Isotherms and (b) Streamlines for various Pr and $Ra = 10^4$, $Ha = 60$, $\phi = 5^\circ$ in the cavity

Fig. 5. (a). Isotherms and (b) Streamlines in the cavity for various Pr while $Ha = 60$, $Ra=10^4$, $\phi=20^\circ$

Fig. 6. (a). Isotherms and (b) Streamlines for various Pr while $Ha = 60$, $Ra=10^4$, $\phi = 35^\circ$ in the cavity

Fig. 8. Line graphs of total Heat Flux for Pr = 0.72, 2, 5, 7, while Ha = 60, Ra=10⁴, φ = 0°

Fig. 9. Line graphs of total Heat Flux for Pr = 0.72, 2, 5, 7, while Ha = 60, Ra=10⁴, φ = 5° in the cavity

Fig. 10. Line graphs of total Heat Flux for Pr = 0.72, 2, 5, 7, while Ha = 60, Ra=10⁴, φ = 20°

Fig. 11. Line graphs of total Heat Flux for Pr = 0.72, 2, 5, 7, while Ha = 60, Ra=10⁴, φ = 35° in the cavity

Fig. 12. Line graphs of total Heat Flux for Pr = 0.72, 2, 5, 7, while Ha = 60, Ra=10⁴, φ = 50° in the cavity

Table 1. Heat flux for various angles and Pr while Ha = 60, Ra = 10⁴

Angle = φ	0°	5°	20°	35°	50°
Heat flux for Pr = 0.72	5400	5400	4900	4000	2200
Heat flux for Pr = 2.0	7500	7500	5100	4500	2300
Heat flux for Pr = 5.0	25500	28000	20100	19000	9000
Heat flux for Pr = 7.0	45000	49500	40000	36000	25500

The effects of Prandtl number on heat flux in the cavity for various inclination angles are shown in the line graphs from Figs. 8 to 12 and these results are tabulated in the Table 1 above for Ha = 60. The line graphs in Figs. 8 to 12 show that heat flux is maximum when Prandtl number Pr is maximum but heat flux is affected inversely by inclination angle of the cavity from 5° to 50°. It is found that heat flux is maximum at inclination angle 5° for variation of Pr.

4. CONCLUSION

Finite element method is used to solve the present physical problem and analyze the effects of inclination angles 0° to 50° on heat flux and fluid flow for steady-state, incompressible, laminar and MHD free convection flow in a square open cavity containing a heated circular cylinder. The flow with Ra = 10000 in this work has been affected by the buoyancy force. Temperature fields are illustrated in the flow

region. The high temperature region remains at the lower portion near the open side of the cavity and the isothermal lines are nonlinear for all inclination angles used in this study and they occupied almost half of the region of the cavity near the open side. The significant findings of this work are that for all cases of inclinations and Ra the isothermal lines concentrated to the right lower corner of the cavity and there are recirculations around the cylinder counterclockwise and one small vortex has been created in the flow field while angle 45° and $Pr = 0.72$. Inclination angle inversely affects on Heat flux from angle 5° to 50° . That s heat flux is maximum when inclination angle is 5° . If inclination angel increases then heat flux decreases. The streamline are in laminar form in flow field in the cavity.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

1. Alfven Hannse. Existence of electromagnetic-hydrodynamic waves. *Nature*. 1942;150:405–406. Available:[Bibcode:1942Natur.150..405A](#) DOI: 10.1038/150405d0
2. Taylor C, Hood P. A Numerical solution of the Navier-Stoke's equations using finite element technique *International Journal of Computational Fluids*. 1973;1:73-89.
3. Chan YL, Tien CL. A numerical study of two-dimensional laminar natural convection in a shallow open cavity. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*. 1985;28:603-612.
4. Ostrach S, MHD natural convection in a laterally and volumetrically heated square cavity. *ASME Journal of Heat Transfer*. 1988;110:1175-1190.
5. Buchanan GR. Finite element analysis. Schaum's out lines, McGraw Hill; 1994. ISBN: 0-07-008714-8
6. Mohammad A. Natural convection in open cavities and slots. *Journal of Numerical Heat Transfer*. 1995;27:705-716.
7. Sparrow EM, Abraham JP. A new buoyancy model replacing the standard pseudo- density difference for internal natural convection in gases. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*. 2003;45:3583-3591.
8. Roy S, Bosak T. Finite element analysis of natural convection flows in a square cavity with non-uniformly heated wall (s). *Int. Journal of Engineering Science*. 2005;43: 668-1453.
9. Sarris IE, Kakarantzas SC, Grecos AP, Vlachos NS. MHD natural convection in a laterally and volumetrically heated square cavity. *Int. J. of Heat and Mass Transfer*. 2005;48(16):3443-3453.
10. Bilgen E, Oztop H. Natural convection heat transfer in partially open inclined square cavities. *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer*. 2005;48:1470-1479.
11. Ben Nakhi M, Iftekhari M, Loveday DI. Natural convection heat transfer in a partially open square cavity with fin attested to the wall. *ASME Journal of Heat Transfer*; 2008.
12. Pervin S, Nasrin R, Analysis of the flow and heat transfer characteristics for MHD free convection in an enclosure with a heated obstacle. *Nonlinear Analysis. Modeling and Control*. 2011;16(1):89-99.
13. Hossain SA, Alim MA. Effects of natural convection from an open square cavity containing a heated circular cylinder. *BJSIR, Dhaka*. 2012;47(1):19-28.
14. Saha SC. Effect of MHD and heat generation on natural convection flow in an open square cavity under microgravity condition. *Int. Journal of Engineering Computations- Australia*. 2013;30:5-20.

© 2017 Hossain et al.; This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Peer-review history:
The peer review history for this paper can be accessed here:
<http://sciencedomain.org/review-history/19393>